

CARE₄ DAIRY

Mini-review

Thermal comfort of dairy cows

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1. The issue

There has been growing interest in studying the effects of heat stress in dairy cows as it consists a welfare and production issue in temperate latitudes as well as the tropics, which is expected to increase in the near future. According to recent projections, global temperatures are expected to rise by 1.4–3.0°C by the end of this century, and by 5.0°C in certain temperate regions of the planet. An average temperature increase of 2°C or more is also expected in the coming years, along with an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme heat waves. (Galan et al., 2018; Bernabucci, 2019; Carvajal et al., 2021).

The effects of climate change on dairy cattle result from the combined effects of changes in air temperature, precipitation patterns, and the occurrence of extreme weather events. These effects include both direct and indirect effects. Specifically, heat stress results from the cumulative influence of external factors that raise the body temperature of homeothermic organisms, such as dairy cows, above their normal resting state. This, in turn, triggers physiological responses. Several studies (Hansen and Aréchiga, 1999; Polsky and von Keyserlingk, 2017; Huber et al., 2020) have investigated this phenomenon.

Under nonstressing conditions, the term "thermoneutral zone" refers to the range of environmental temperatures in which body heat production remains minimal, allowing for normal body temperature regulation (Kadzere et al., 2002). In dairy cows, this thermoneutral zone typically extends from about 5°C to 25°C (Dovolou et al., 2023). Temperatures outside of this range cause discomfort, and dairy cows have a reduced ability to effectively regulate their body temperature when exposed to ambient temperatures above the upper limit of the thermoneutral zone (Armstrong, 1994; Kadzere et al., 2002; Huber et al., 2020).

The Temperature-Humidity Index (THI) serves as a comprehensive metric that takes into account both ambient temperature and relative humidity to assess the intensity of heat stress and represent thermal climatic conditions (Du Preez, 2000; Prasanna, 2021). THI is determined using dry and wet bulb air temperatures according to the formula $[THI = 0.72 (Wb + Db) + 40.6]$ established by the National Research Council (NRC) in 1971. Recent research (Pinto et al., 2020) has identified specific THI thresholds for various physiological parameters in cows, such as respiration rate in standing cows (THI=70), lying cows (THI=65), heart rate (THI=72), and rectal temperature (THI=70) in standing cows.

Climate change increases the need for adaptation and mitigation strategies that include a range of available tools in areas such as management, nutrition, housing, breeding and genetics (Giménez-Benavides et al., 2018; Gauly et al., 2020).

2. Summary of the scientific knowledge¹

The potential impacts of changing climatic conditions on dairy cattle can be assessed by using animal-based or resource-based indicators, or a combination of both, as suggested by Gauly et al. (2020). The disruption of thermal comfort in these cattle is influenced by a variety of factors, as highlighted by Galan et al. (2018) and Yan et al. (2022).

The impact of climate change on the dairy industry is already evident and will continue to manifest itself in both direct and indirect ways. The indirect effects on dairy production systems can be categorised based on factors such as the availability and quality of feed and water, the prevalence of disease, and the distribution of disease vectors. Taken together, these factors have a negative impact on the health and performance of dairy cattle. These effects include reduced production levels, higher mortality rates, impaired immune function, an increased incidence of infectious diseases, reproductive problems, changes in feed consumption and growth, and reduced milk yield, particularly in high yielding dairy cattle. These effects in turn lead to economic disadvantages. There is therefore an urgent need to develop effective mitigation and adaptation strategies. These strategies should encompass multiple aspects, including husbandry practices, management approaches, nutritional considerations, animal health, and plant and animal breeding, such as selection for heat tolerance. Such measures are essential to provide long-term solutions to address these challenges (Gauly et al., 2020).

From a physiological point of view, dairy cows start to reduce their feed intake at air temperatures around 25–26°C. This reduction in dry matter intake serves as a mechanism to mitigate heat production in warm environmental conditions, as observed in the study conducted by Fournel et al. (2017). Specifically, heat-stressed cows typically reduce their dry matter intake by approximately 10 to 15% compared to cows kept in cooler conditions. Heat stressed cows also exhibit increased respiration and sweating rates, resulting in increased fluid loss from the body. This increases the need for maintenance to counteract dehydration and maintain blood homeostasis. As a result, heat-induced reductions in milk yield can be substantial, reaching up to 14% in early lactation and 35% in mid-lactation. Disruption of thermal comfort also affects reproduction in dairy cows, as it reduces the expression of estrous behavior, alters follicular growth, and impedes embryonic development, leading to increased early embryo mortality and reduced fertility, particularly in high-yielding dairy cows, as highlighted by Fournel et al. (2017) and Nanas et al. (2021).

In terms of behavior, dairy cows employ coping strategies in response to the degree of thermal comfort disturbance. These behavioural adaptations typically include changes in

¹ The scientific reviews prepared for CARE4DAIRY focused on the literature of the last 10 years, assuming that older articles have already been taken into account in current technical recommendations. Older articles may be cited if they provide complementary knowledge.

motor activity, resting patterns, preferences for sheltered areas or shaded pastures, adjustments in feeding behaviour, and changes in social interactions, as highlighted by Herbut et al. (2021). These behavioral changes may also affect the performance of robotic milking systems, as a mere 1°C increase in mean daily temperature was found to reduce rumination time by approximately 5.12 min per day, decrease rumination efficiency by 0.07 kg per cow per hour, and increase the incidence of low efficiency milking by 1%, as reported by Ji et al. (2020a,b).

The lack of thermal comfort has a significant impact on several aspects of dairy cow biology beyond reduced productivity. Indeed it can impact on physiological and molecular processes. The expression of mRNA and miRNA - key players in the response to chronic heat stress - is altered in dairy cows during their transition from heat-stress conditions to a thermoneutral environment (Liu et al., 2020). In addition, increased free radical production, resulting in heat-induced mitochondrial damage, may contribute to inability of cells' to meet the increased energy demands of heat-stressed animals (Belhadj Slimen et al., 2016).

In dairy cows, resilience to thermal discomfort refers to the ability of animals to respond to thermal challenges by maintaining thermal balance and restoring homeostasis. Indicators of this resilience, based on animal behavior, can include locomotor responses (e.g., standing to expose more surface area to airflow), physiological responses (e.g., increased panting, sweating, and drooling), and changes in the feeding behaviour (e.g., reduced feed intake). All of these adaptations have a common goal: to regulate body temperature by either reducing metabolic heat production or increasing heat loss through mechanisms such as conduction, convection, radiation, and water evaporation. Failure of these mechanisms results in elevated body temperature and the associated heat stress response. At the same time, as predicted climate changes unfold, they are expected to exert selective pressure on traits critical for biological fitness and resilience (Galan et al., 2018).

the response of dairy cow to heat stress is influence by various factors (Galan et al., 2018):

- Genetic and phenotypic background: different breeds and crosses of dairy cows can have different responses to hot conditions. For instance, Holstein cows tend to have higher internal temperatures during hot weather compared to other breeds such as Jersey or Brown Swiss.
- Metabolic status: The susceptibility of cows to heat stress can be influenced by their metabolic status, which, in turn, affects heat production. Factors such as lactation and gestation can significantly alter metabolic heat production in cattle.
- Duration of heat challenge: Circadian rhythms play a role in how cows respond to heat stress, with body temperatures being lower in the morning than in the afternoon.

- Type of systems and management: The term "cooling systems" encompasses various designs involving fans, often combined with misters or sprinklers, installed in barns to mitigate heat stress.
- Underlying factors influencing resting behaviour: Resting behaviour can be influenced by several factors is an indicator of heat stress. For instance, lying down helps to remove heat by convection, and wind speed can affect the rate of convection and therefore the amount of time heat stressed cows spend standing.

Long-term effects of heat stress: There may be a delay of two days between temperature exposure to heat stress and the decrease in milk production (Ji et al., 2020c,d,e). The detrimental effects of heat stress depends not only on its intensity, but also on its duration and the cumulative effects of previous exposures. For instance, heat stress effects can persist for several months, e.g. heat stress experienced during the dry-off period can influence milk production during subsequent lactation.

3. Recommendations

Modifying the environment: A wide range of strategies are available to counteract the adverse effects of a hot climate on animal production and dairy profitability, a wide range of strategies are available, with the primary approach being the physical modification of the environment. These strategies can be broadly categorized into two groups: (i) those that modify the environment to prevent or minimise the extent of heat stress experienced by cows; and (ii) those that enhance the heat exchange processes between cows and their environment. In practical terms, this include increasing the rate of evaporative cooling, achieved by wetting the cows or the air around them (for instance, through the use of misters and sprinklers), and improving convective heat transfer by increasing the airflow over the cows (often achieved by using fans and optimizing barn ventilation). In addition, maintaining a consistent source of shade, particularly in areas such as feeding and watering stations, and adjusting grazing practices during cooler periods can further help to alleviate heat stress (Fournel et al., 2017).

Feeding strategies: There is a variety of feeding strategies exists that have demonstrated the potential to effectively mitigate the effects of heat stress effectively. These strategies encompass several aspects, including the judicious supplementation of dietary fat, minerals, trace elements, and vitamins, reducing dietary fibre content, incorporating microbial ingredients (particularly yeast), utilising plant extracts, and introducing other additives that show promise in enhancing antioxidant and immune functions (Min et al., 2019; Shan et al., 2020). In the future, there is potential for the development of probiotic supplements for feed rations. In addition, during periods of heat stress, it is imperative to increase the supply of bicarbonate, potassium, vitamin C, and vitamin B3 in the feed rations. Providing continuous access to cool, clean water throughout the day is another

important measure. In addition, increasing the energy density of the feed ration serves as a critical step to compensate for any potential reduction in feed intake during heat stress (Kadzere et al., 2002; Sossidou et al., 2014; Herbut et al., 2021).

Non-invasive methods for measuring individual parameters in dairy cows, based on precision technologies (Hoffman et al., 2020; Molina et al., 2020; Tsai et al., 2020):

Parameter	Body surface	Technology
Internal temperature	Rectum	Digital thermometer, radio transmitter
	Vagina	Microprocessorcontrolled data loggers, radio transmitter
	Rumen	Rumen bolus
	Ear canal	Tympanic infrared thermometer, telemetry transmitter
External temperature	Surface temperature of body part	Infrared thermography camera (picture- or video-based), thermal imaging scanner, button-shaped digital thermo-loggers upon skin, thermistor sensors
Respiration rate	Flank, chest, nostrils	Visual count of flank movements, chest belt, laser distance sensor, thermistor, differential pressure sensor
Heart rate	Cardiac region	Chest belt with electrodes and recording unit
Individual adaptability	Shade seeking, brush use, aggression	Video recordings and analysis (supported by evaluation software)
Activity	Standing, lying, locomotion/ leg, rumen, collar	(tri-axial) accelerometers, gyrometer, GPS, wireless radiotracking, video-based
Rumination	Halter, collar	Observation, recording via microphone or pressure sensor between nose and halter
Feeding/Drinking	Feed intake, dry matter intake, drinking	Camera systems, GPS, collar, in trough integrated scales, embedded imaging systems
Milk yield	Milking technologies	Tilt trays, herd management software
Milk constituents	Milk fat, -protein, -lactose, solid non-fat	Milking technologies, laboratory

4. Literature search

Search equation in WOS: (thermal comfort) AND (heat stress) AND (dairy cows),
December 2021-March 2023

Number of results: 314

Selection process: 36 publications kept

No. publications excluded	Reasons for exclusion
96	Not on dairy cattle (incl. zebu)
128	Only on husbandry systems in the tropics
54	Not on thermal comfort (generally on welfare)

A reference on extended lactation in dairy cows was added.

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